

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DEEP WATER

Effect of stem borer (SB) at different internodes of deep water rice

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We studied the effect of SB *Scirpophaga incertulas* on growth and yield of deep water rice. The crop was grown on a 0.2-ha field that was thoroughly plowed before planting in 1983 kharif.

Photoperiod-sensitive Jaladhi 1 was direct-seeded in early Jun. Soil was a clay loam with pH 7.0-7.5. Farmyard manure at 10 t/ha was applied at land preparation, and standard cultivation was practiced. Weekly water level was recorded. Maximum depth was 160 cm in mid-Oct. The crop was harvested in late Dec and plant samples were collected.

SB damage was determined based on borer infestation at different internodes and their effect on growth and yield of the infested shoot. Plants were divided into three groups

- those without SB damage,
- those with SB damage only on the terminal internode, and
- those with SB at the 2d to 12th internodes.

For each group, 20 plants were randomly selected from the deep water plot and up-

Growth and yield of healthy and SB-infested deep water rice plants, West Bengal, India.

Character	Healthy	Infested plants		CD at 5%
		Terminal internode	Other internodes	
Plant height (cm)	315	303	305	ns
Stem length (cm)	289	268	279	ns
Internodes (no.)	15	16	15	ns
Panicle length (cm)	26	26	25	ns
Spikelets (no.)	181	175	147	25
Grain sterility (%)	19	100	30	3
100-grain weight (g)	2.1	—	2.1	ns
Grain yield (g)	3.1	—	2.2	0.7
Fresh weight (g)	24.4	33.2	24.4	7.8
Dry weight (g)	9.5	9.4	8.2	ns
Water content (g)	14.9	23.8	16.2	6.3

rooted. Main stem performance was analyzed.

Although plants without SB damage had better plant height, stem length, internode number, and dry weight, they were not significantly different from infested plants. Fresh weight and water content were significantly different at different infestation levels (see table). Panicle emergence and length did not vary significantly between infestations.

SB infestation significantly affected most yield characters. Plants with infestation between the 2d and 12th internodes yielded some grain, but with infestation of the terminal internode there was no yield. Infestation reduced the number of filled grains per panicle, not 100-grain

weight (see table).

Feeding in the inner tissues of terminal internodes stopped grain filling and withered apical plant parts. When submerged lower internodes were infested, reproductive growth, vigor, dry matter accumulation, and grain yield declined, but results were not so serious as with later infestation.

The thick cortex and enlarged parenchymatous cells in lower internodes prevent SB from boring into the vascular tissue and appreciably disturbing the ascent of sap and translocation of solutes. Additionally, infestation of lower internodes causes development of aquatic roots that absorb nutrients. □

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RAINFED

Early rices for rainfed uplands

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At NDUAT we have identified three new rice lines with good production potential. NDR84 (IET7988) and NDR85 (IET7989)

Table 1. Performance of some elite lines at Faizabad under direct seeded rainfed upland culture in wet season 1981 to 1983.

Line, variety	Maturity (d)	Plant height (cm)	Grain type	Yield (t/ha)			
				1981	1982	1983	Mean
NDR84	99	78	Long slender	3.4	3.4	4.6	3.8
NDR85	93	87	Long slender	4.2	3.2	3.7	3.7
NDR118	95	83	Longslender	—	3.8	4.7	4.2
N22 (local tall check)	85	100	Short bold	2.4	2.1	3.5	2.7
Cauvery (semidwarf check)	99	84	Short bold	2.2	2.8	2.7	2.6
CD 0.05				0.8	0.3	0.6	
Rainfall (mm)				1488	1169	1261	
Sowing date				1 Jul	21 Jun	9 Jul	
				81	82	83	

Table 2. Performance of some elite lines in AICRIP trials under direct seeded rainfed upland conditions in India in 1982 and 1983 wet season.

Location	Yield (t/ha)					CD 0.05	Wet season rainfall (mm)
	NDR84	NDR85	NDR118 ^a	Akashi	Cauvery		
<i>1982</i>							
Faizabad, Uttar Pradesh	5.2	4.8	5.4	4.6	3.5	0.7	1082
Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh	4.1	4.6	5.4	4.2	4.0	1.2	851
Nagina, Uttar Pradesh	4.6	3.8	5.4	1.2	4.3	1.2	948
Ranchi, Bihar	1.7	2.8	5.4	1.2	1.9	0.8	794
Hazaribagh, Bihar	3.1	2.6	5.4	2.9	2.8	0.5	774
Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh	4.5	4.3	5.4	3.9	4.4	1.2	—
Jeypore, Orissa	3.4	5.1	5.4	3.0	1.2	1.5	1417
Mean	3.8	4.0	5.4	3.0	3.16		
<i>1983</i>							
Faizabad, Uttar Pradesh	5.8	3.6	5.4	2.5	3.1	0.61	1261
Nagina, Uttar Pradesh	2.5	4.2	5.4	2.4	0.7	1.57	599
Ranchi, Bihar	2.3	3.4	5.4	2.1	2.0	0.64	1108
Hazaribagh, Bihar	1.8	2.7	5.4	2.4	1.7	0.12	914
Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh	2.9	2.6	5.4	3.5	2.7	1.00	1504
Rewa, Madhya Pradesh	2.0	2.7	5.4	2.6	1.7	0.48	1263
Bhuaneshwar, Orissa	2.4	1.5	5.4	1.9	1.2	1.15	—
Bankura, West Bengal	1.9	2.1	5.4	1.2	1.5	0.18	916
Hathwara, West Bengal	2.0	2.9	5.4	—	1.3	1.03	898
Karimganj, Assam	4.5	3.7	5.4	2.8	1.9	0.55	—
Titabar, Assam	1.7	1.2	5.4	1.3	0.7	0.73	293
Karjat, Maharashtra	3.4	1.5	5.4	2.7	1.4	0.52	—
Dhaulakuwan, Maharashtra	2.4	3.0	5.4	2.8	1.3	1.12	—
Mean	2.7	2.7	5.4	2.8	1.5		

^a Not grown in 1982.

are sister selections from N22/IR2071-625-252 (IR36), and NDR118 (IET8681) is a selection from IR2071-625-252/Hansraj 'A'. The lines have semidwarf stature and long slender grains. They consistently outyielded the tall local check N22 and the semidwarf national check Cauvery at Faizabad from 1981 to 1983 (Table 1), and are resistant to most foliage diseases. They also were tested at other locations in 1982 and 1983 wet seasons under the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program (AICRIP), and performed better than varieties Akashi and Cauvery (Table 2).

NDR118 is a 95-d variety and thus suitable for rotation with wheat, potato, mustard, and vegetables in north central India. □

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Screening rices for rainfed direct-seeded upland cultivation

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In West Bengal, upland rice depends mostly on premonsoon rain. The cropping season is from Mar to Sep, depending on the onset of premonsoon rains. Average yield is 1.4 t/ha because of the harsh environment and lack of suitable varieties. The following limit crop growth and productivity:

- drought during vegetative phase or ripening,
- weeds,
- difficult fertilizer management because of rapid water percolation, and
- poor recovery after drought.

We screened 18 varieties, with Dular as trial check, for performance under different climatic conditions in 1982-83.

In 1982, most study sites had frequent, severe drought spells in vegetative and

Mean yield and frequency distribution of yield, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Frequency distribution of yield in t/ha						Mean yield (t/ha)
	<1.0	<1.5	<2.0	<2.5	<3.0	>3.0	
<i>1982</i>							
BG367-4	3	2	0	1	1	0	1.3
BG367-7	4	0	0	2	0	1	1.4
B9c-Md-3-3	3	1	1	1	1	0	1.5
BKNLR75091	3	1	1	1	0	1	1.4
CNT-B3-RST-40-2-2							
BW242-5-5	3	1	0	2	1	0	1.5
CR237-1	3	2	1	1	0	0	1.2
Dular	2	2	1	2	0	0	1.5
IET7255	4	1	1	0	1	0	1.2
IET7259	3	0	1	1	1	1	1.8
IR50	2	2	3	0	0	0	1.1
IR9209-47-1-1-6-2	3	1	0	2	1	0	1.4
IR9279-67-3	3	1	0	2	1	0	1.5
IR9708-51-1-2	4	0	1	2	0	0	1.2
IR8608-189-2-2-1-3	3	1	0	1	2	0	1.5
IR13204-24-1-6	3	1	2	1	0	0	1.2
Kiran	2	0	1	3	1	0	1.8
Panke	3	0	1	0	2	1	1.9
Suweon	287	3	1	2	0	0	1.4
Mean							1.4
CD at 5%							0.4
<i>1983</i>							
BG367-4	0	1	3	3	1	1	2.2
BG367-7	1	1	3	1	1	2	2.5
B9c-Md-3-3	1	2	1	2	1	2	2.0
BKNLR75091							
CNT-B3-RST40-2-2							
BW242-5-5	0	3	2	0	1	3	2.3
	2	2	1	4	0	0	1.7